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Social-phenomenological approach to the analysis of virtual communications

Modern researchers of communication problems believe that philosophical analysis can enrich each part of the cognitive map of social sciences, presented in the form of a matrix. However, philosophical analysis of communication today faces the problem of conceptual uncertainty of this concept in philosophical discourse. Despite the desire of science for «conceptual rigor and clarity», the content of the concept of communication remains one of the most context-dependent and semantically uncertain [1].

It can be argued that the content of the concept of communication in modern philosophy is determined by the contexts in which it is used. This complicates the application of the concept of communication to solve specific problems of cognitive social sciences. In modern philosophical literature, the concept of «communication» is associated with such categories as social, individual, context and intersubjectivity. Intersubjectivity mediates the dichotomy of the social and individual, has three main interpretations, which determines three approaches to the analysis of communication, including virtual communication.

The first approach sees intersubjectivity as an absolute opposition of the social and the individual, presented in dualistic metaphysics. Here, the individual is considered an isolated entity, and the social as an objective reality opposing the individual. The main problem of this approach is the transcendence of individuality, where intersubjectivity either creates bridges between the two poles or eliminates one of them. The second approach partially overcomes dualism, offering a model of interpenetrating social and individual. Here, each retains its independent nature, but exists only in the context of relationships. This approach, known as «mutual belonging», describes communication as a process of decontextualization and recontextualization. However, the problem is that it presupposes the existence of a

social context that determines the interaction of individuals. The third approach, rooted in the phenomenological tradition, focuses on the experience of living social reality. This approach examines how individuals perceive others in everyday life and how they constitute themselves as social beings. The advantage of this approach is that it avoids metaphysical connotations and focuses on the constitution of the meaning of intersubjectivity, which makes it the most promising for the study of social communications. This phenomenological approach will be the subject of our further consideration.

The specificity of the socio-phenomenological approach to the analysis of communications in virtual reality lies in the transfer of human meanings through cultural and anthropological processes. Meaning, being a key concept in the philosophy of man, mediates the ontological gap between being and consciousness [2]. Phenomenology studies the semantic structure of social reality. In virtual reality communications, both the situation and objects involved acquire different meanings for each participant. This variation stems from individual perception, where personal experience in the virtual world mediates all forms of perception through subjective meanings.

The primary challenge in virtual reality communication is that participants cannot perceive the same situation identically due to individual differences. Social phenomenology proposes two idealizing assumptions to address this: interchangeability of points of view and coincidence of relevance systems. Interchangeability suggests that differences do not hinder perceiving an object within the same typifications. The fractal nature of virtual reality adds complexity by creating nested layers of meaning and context, requiring participants to navigate these layers for mutual understanding. Coincidence of relevance systems means that, unless proven otherwise, perceptual differences do not obstruct communication [3]. Coincidence of relevance systems means that, until proven otherwise, differences in perception do not prevent communication.

There are multiple levels of understanding other people's actions. For the purposes of virtual communication, it is sufficient to reduce a partner's actions to

typical subjective motives, meaning to relate them to standard situations, goals, and means. In virtual communication, interactions tend to be relatively «soft» due to the physical distance between interlocutors. It is difficult to impose rigid communicative patterns; even if the situation is organized rigidly, interactions in the process of exchanging meanings inevitably become «softened» by the specifics of virtual reality, which allows distancing from destructive interactions.

Virtual communication relies on the use of signs and sign systems. A sign used in communication is addressed either to a specific individual or to an anonymous interpreter. Communication will be successful if the sign used by the sender is interpreted in the way the receiver expects. Phenomenologically, this means that the sender must anticipate the interpretative schemas of the recipient. In other words, the sender must anticipate how their words will be perceived and «rehearse» their interpretation by the partner. The success of virtual communication depends on the degree of alignment between the sender's and the recipient's interpretative schemas. Absolute alignment of interpretative schemas is impossible due to differences in personal systems of subjective meanings, which are determined by various situations. The communicative imperative of virtual communication can be formulated as follows: the alignment of the meaning context of interpretative schemas determines the conditions and limits of possible communication, that is, the ability of partners to understand each other adequately.

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